

Report
Design and optimisation of 5-Cell Cavities for the
 $t\bar{t}$ Working Point of the FCC-ee Considering
Higher-Order Mode Effects

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1 SRF Description for FCC-ee $t\bar{t}$ Working Point

The Future Circular electron-positron Collider (FCC-ee) is planned to operate with beam energies from 45.6 to 182.5 GeV and beam currents from 5 to 1400 mA [1]. The purpose is to study the properties of the Z-, W- and Higgs bosons and the top and anti-top quarks. Four operating points are defined for the study. These are the Z, W, H and $t\bar{t}$ operating points. The Z operating point has the highest beam current and lowest beam energy. Beam energy increases from the Z operating point to the $t\bar{t}$ operating point while the beam current decreases, in the same manner, maintaining a total synchrotron radiation power loss P_{SR} of 50 MW per beam.

Previous studies have been carried out on the Z, W, H and $t\bar{t}$ working points [2, 3]. For the Z operating point, a 1-cell superconducting radio-frequency (SRF) elliptical cavity is designed to operate at an accelerating electric field of 5.72 MV/m because of the high beam current. A 2-cell SRF elliptical cavity was designed for the W and H operating points set to operate at an accelerating electric field of 11.91 and 11.87 MV/m, respectively [4]. Table 1 shows the parameters of the operating points. For the $t\bar{t}$ operating point, a 5-cell SRF elliptical cavity was designed to operate at an accelerating field of 24.72 MV/m.

This report aims to investigate if the performance of the designed cavity for the $t\bar{t}$ operating point can be improved upon, especially concerning higher-order modes (HOMs) effects. Also, considering the high beam current of 140 mA for the Z booster, by improving the HOM characteristics of the 5-cell cavities, the same type of 5-cell 800 MHz cavities can be used for the boosters of all four operating points.

Section 2 presents the updated FCC-ee machine parameters for the different operating points. The radio-frequency (RF) requirements are briefly described for the $t\bar{t}$ operating point. Challenges of the design are also highlighted. The current baseline cavity for the $t\bar{t}$ operating point is hereafter referred to as the FCCUROS5. In section 3, the method of cavity optimisation is outlined, and constraints are discussed. The properties of the designed cavity are presented in this section. In section 4, the properties of the designed cavity are compared with those of the baseline cavity. The properties of the TESLA cavity are included in this comparison for reference, as the TESLA cavity is a well-established cavity design.

Lastly, there has been a question about the cavity type (2-cell or 5-cell) and operating frequency (400.79MHz or 801.58 MHz) most suitable for the H working point. In section 5, a comparison of the figures of merit for some options is made.

2 FCC-ee Machine Parameters

The machine parameters for the FCC-ee are constantly being updated. Table 1 gives the history of some critical parameters for RF design. The beam current for the Z working point increased by 10 mA from 1390 mA to 1400 mA while the

current for the other working points decreased. The beam energy has remained the same. The RF voltage increased for all operating points except for the $t\bar{t}$ operating point, for which the RF voltage decreased. There is a drastic reduction in the number of bunches for the Z and W operating points by about 50% and an increase in the bunch intensity by roughly the same percentage. The luminosity decreased for all operating points.

Table 1: Some machine parameters for the FCC-ee in 2018 [1], 2020 [5] and 2022 [6].

	Z			W			H			$t\bar{t}$		
	2018	2020	2022	2018	2020	2022	2018	2020	2022*	2018*	2020*	2022*
Beam energy [GeV]		45.6			80			120			182.5	
Beam current/beam [mA]	1390	1390	1400	147	147	135	29	29	26.7	5.4	5.4	5
RF volt. 400/800 MHz [GV]	0.1	0.1	0.12/-	0.75	0.44	1.0/-	2.0/-	2.0/-	2.1/-	4/5.4	10.9/-	2.5/8.8
SR loss/turn [MeV]	36	36	38.49	340	340	364.6	1720	1720	1845.94	9200	9210	9875.14
No. of bunches/beam	16640	16640	8800	2000	2000	1120	328	393	336	48	48	42
Bunch intensity [10^{11}]	1.7	1.7	2.76	1.5	1.5	2.29	1.8	1.5	1.51	2.3	2.3	2.26
Bunch SR length [mm]	3.5	3.5	4.32	3	3	3.55	3.15	3.3	2.5	1.97	2.0	1.67
Bunch BS length [mm]	12.1	12.1	15.2	6	6	7.02	5.3	5.3	4.45	2.54	2.5	2.54
Luminosity [$10^{34}\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$]	230	230	181	28	28	17.3	8.5	8.5	7.2	1.55	1.55	1.25

*For these operating points, the two beams are assumed to be accelerated by the same RF system.

2.1 The $t\bar{t}$ Operating Point

The centre of mass energy of the top and anti-top quark is $171.77 \pm 0.38\text{GeV}$ [7]. To study the properties of the top and anti-top quark, beams of 5 mA are to be accelerated to an energy of 182.5 GeV before colliding with each other. For this purpose, a 5-cell elliptical accelerating cavity operating at a fundamental mode (FM) frequency of 801.58 MHz and an accelerating field of 24.72 MV/m is proposed [4]. The cavity is to be manufactured using bulk Niobium maintained at 2 K. A comparison of the surface resistance of bulk Niobium at 2 K and 800 MHz with some other material options is shown in Figure 1. A stringent limit of this operating point is Niobium's critical surface magnetic field at 2 K, which is about 200 mT [8, p. 45][9].

2.2 Baseline Cavity

The FCCURO5 is a cavity geometry design proposed for the $t\bar{t}$ working point [2, p. 68]. Figure 4 shows the cavity's parameterised mid-cell and end-cell geometries. The geometric properties for the FCCURO5 are presented in Table 2. The FM quantities of interest (QoIs) for the bare cavity are shown in Table 3, and the HOM QoIs are specified in Table 4.

The impedance properties of the cavity from Figure 6.20 in [2] are plotted in Figures 2 and 3, respectively. Figures 2 and 3 show the longitudinal and transverse impedance plots for different HOM damping schemes of a four 5-cell cavity module, respectively.

Figure 1: Surface resistance R_s of some accelerating cavity wall materials [2, p. 35]. Nb/Cu represents niobium-coated copper, and bulkNb represents bulk niobium.

Table 2: Geometric parameters of FCCUROS5. Subscripts i and e distinguish between the mid-cell and end-cell geometric parameters.

FCCUROS5 - Geometric Parameters							
A_i/A_e	B_i/B_e	a_i/a_e	b_i/b_e	$R_{i,i}/R_{i,e}$	L_i/L_e	R_{eq}	$\alpha_i/\alpha_e [^\circ]$
67.72/66.50	57.45/51.00	21.75/17.00	35.95/23.00	60.00/78.00	93.50/85.77	166.591	100.00/96.87

All dimensions in mm except specified.

Table 3: FM QoIs of FCCUROS5.

FCCUROS5 - FM QoIs						
No. of cells	R/Q [Ω]	G [Ω]	$G.R/Q$ [$10^4 \Omega^2$]	E_{pk}/E_{acc} [.]	B_{pk}/E_{acc} [mT/MV/m]	
5	521.06	272.93	14.22	2.05	4.33	

Table 4: HOM QoIs of FCCUROS5.

FCCUROS5 - HOM QoIs			
No. of cells	$ k_{ } $ [SR/BS] [V/pC]	k_{\perp} [SR/BS] [V/pC/m]	$P_{HOM}/cav/beam$ [SR/BS] [W]
5	3.784/2.908	3.539/4.102	1132.66/815.75

$k_{||}$ and k_{\perp} are calculated for the bare cavity.

The damping schemes are labelled as follows:

- 2DQW1QRWG - Two double quarter-wave (DQW) HOM couplers and one quad-ridged waveguide (QRWG) HOM coupler,
- 2DQW1RWG - Two DQW HOM couplers and one rectangular waveguide (RWG) HOM coupler,
- 2DQW - Two DQW HOM couplers,
- 2RWG - Two RWG couplers,
- 2H2P - Two hook-type (H) couplers and two probe-type (P) couplers.

The impedance values are compared with the longitudinal and transverse impedance thresholds calculated from the 2018 and 2022 machine parameter sets. Figures 2 and 3 show an increase in the longitudinal and transverse impedance threshold values for the $t\bar{t}$ operating point. The 2022 impedance threshold is labelled $t\bar{t}_{2022}$, and the 2018 is labelled $t\bar{t}_{2018}$. The plots show that the calculated maximum longitudinal and transverse impedance values for the four-cavity 5-cell (FCCUROS5) module are below the present threshold values implying that the cavity is still suitable for operation at the $t\bar{t}$ operating point.

Figure 2: Longitudinal impedance plot of HOM damped four 5-cell cavity module. The impedance thresholds are normalised to the number of modules required for the $t\bar{t}$ operating point.

This study presents an alternative design with more focus on the HOM properties of the cavity at the expense of its FM properties, thus opening the way for increasing the beam current in future upgrades or for using the cavity in the Z, W, H and $t\bar{t}$ booster.

Figure 3: Transverse impedance plot of HOM damped four 5-cell cavity module. The impedance thresholds are normalised to the number of modules required for the $\bar{t}\bar{t}$ operating point.

3 Cavity Design and Optimisation

This section presents the design of an elliptical accelerating cavity geometry. The mid-cell and end-cell geometries of the cavity are optimised separately to reduce the computational costs involved in optimising the whole cavity. After optimisation, multipacting analysis is carried out on the 2D model using the 2D code Multipac [12] to study the multipacting properties of the optimised cavity.

3.1 Cavity Geometry Design

The cavity's geometry design and optimisation are performed in two parts - design and optimisation of the mid-cell and then of the end-cell. Figure 4 shows the parameterised geometry of the mid-cell of typical elliptical cavities. To define the whole geometry, 14 geometric parameters are required. They are $A_i, B_i, a_i, b_i, R_i, L_i, R_{eq,i}, A_e, B_e, a_e, b_e, R_{i,e}, L_e$ and $R_{eq,e}$. The equator radius of the mid-cell and end-cell must be equal for continuity, i.e. $R_{eq,e} = R_{eq,i} = R_{eq}$. The length of the inner half-cell, L_i , is determined by the FM frequency, in this case, $f_0 = 801.58$ MHz. It is calculated as

$$L_i = \frac{\beta c}{4f_0}, \quad (1)$$

where c is the propagation speed of electromagnetic waves in free space, and β is the ratio of beam velocity to the speed of light, approximately one for ultra-relativistic beams.

In searching for an optimised geometry, the geometric parameters, except L_i , were varied. One of the parameters is tuned to ensure that the $TM_{010} - \pi$

mode resonates at the design frequency. The tuned variables for the mid-cell and end-cell are R_{eq} and L_e , respectively.

Figure 4: Parameterised mid-cell (left) and end-cell (right) of an elliptical cavity.

The following QoIs are considered in the optimisation of the cavity's geometry:

- The peak electric and magnetic field to accelerating electric field ratios $E_{\text{pk}}/E_{\text{acc}}$, $B_{\text{pk}}/E_{\text{acc}}$, respectively,
- The ratio of the square of the accelerating field voltage of the FM to the product of angular frequency and the stored energy, R/Q , and
- The maximum longitudinal $\max_{f/\text{GHz} \in [a,b]} |Z_{\parallel}(f)|$ and transverse HOMs impedance $\max_{f/\text{GHz} \in [a,b]} |Z_{\perp}(f)|$ in specified frequency intervals.

The intervals are specified based on the expected frequency range in which the parasitic HOMs occur. Two intervals are defined for the longitudinal HOMs - the interval containing the TM_{011} mode and the second interval for the other longitudinal HOMs. Three impedance intervals are specified for the transverse HOMs. The first interval is defined to capture the maximum transverse HOMs impedance in the first dipole passband. The second interval is defined to capture the peak impedance of the dipole modes with frequencies some MHz greater than the beampipe TE_{11} mode cutoff frequency. The third interval is defined to capture the peak impedance of the other transverse HOMs. The required interval impedances are defined mathematically as follows:

$$|Z_{\parallel,1}| = \max_{f/\text{GHz} \in [1,2]} |Z_{\parallel}(f)|, \quad (2a)$$

$$|Z_{\parallel,2}| = \max_{f/\text{GHz} \in [2,4]} |Z_{\parallel}(f)|, \quad (2b)$$

$$|Z_{\perp,1}| = \max_{f/\text{GHz} \in [0.7,1.3]} |Z_{\perp}(f)|, \quad (2c)$$

$$|Z_{\perp,2}| = \max_{f/\text{GHz} \in [1.3,2.25]} |Z_{\perp}(f)|, \quad (2d)$$

$$|Z_{\perp,3}| = \max_{f/\text{GHz} \in [2.25,4]} |Z_{\perp}(f)|. \quad (2e)$$

The QoIs $E_{\text{pk}}/E_{\text{acc}}$, $B_{\text{pk}}/E_{\text{acc}}$, and R/Q are evaluated from the solution of the Maxwell Eigenvalue Problem (MEVP) which is solved using SLANS [13]. The MEVP is stated as

$$\nabla \times (\mu^{-1} \nabla \times \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x})) - \lambda(\mathbf{x})\epsilon \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}) = 0, \quad \lambda = \frac{\omega^2}{c^2}, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^7, \quad (3a)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = 0 \quad \mathbf{E} \in \Omega, \quad (3b)$$

$$\mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{E} = 0 \quad \mathbf{E} \in \partial\Omega_{\text{wall}}, \quad (3c)$$

$$\mathbf{n} \times (\mu^{-1} \nabla \times \mathbf{E}) = 0 \quad \mathbf{E} \in \partial\Omega, \quad (3d)$$

where ω is angular velocity, \mathbf{x} is a vector of the geometric variables describing the domain Ω with boundary $\partial\Omega_{\text{wall}} \cup \partial\Omega$, \mathbf{n} denotes the outward normal on $\partial\Omega_{\text{wall}} \cup \partial\Omega$, \mathbf{E} is the electric field vector, λ a vector of eigenvalues, μ magnetic permeability and ϵ electrical permittivity.

The longitudinal (Z_{\parallel}) and transverse impedances (Z_{\perp}) are evaluated as the Fourier transform of the wake functions using the following formulas.

$$\begin{aligned} Z_{\parallel}(\omega) &= \frac{1}{c} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} w_{\parallel}(s) e^{(-i\omega s/c)} ds, \\ \mathbf{Z}_{\perp}(\omega) &= \frac{-i}{c} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \mathbf{w}_{\perp}(s) e^{(-i\omega s/c)} ds. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where w_{\parallel} and \mathbf{w}_{\perp} are the longitudinal and transverse wake functions, respectively. The longitudinal and transverse wake functions are solved using ABCI electromagnetic code [14]. They are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} w_{\parallel}(\boldsymbol{\rho}, s) &= \frac{c}{q} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} E_z|_{z=ct-s} dz, \\ \mathbf{w}_{\perp}(\boldsymbol{\rho}, s) &= \frac{c}{q} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (\mathbf{E}_{\perp} + c\hat{z} \times \mathbf{B})|_{z=ct-s} dz, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where s is the distance between the leading and a trailing test particle with offset $\boldsymbol{\rho} = (x, y)$ relative to the z -axis, and z is the direction of travel of the beam.

The optimisation problem for the middle cell is stated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \min_{A_i, B_i, a_i, b_i, R_{i,i}} \left(\frac{E_{\text{pk}}}{E_{\text{acc}}}, \frac{B_{\text{pk}}}{E_{\text{acc}}}, -R/Q, |Z_{\parallel,1}|, |Z_{\parallel,2}|, |Z_{\perp,1}|, |Z_{\perp,2}|, |Z_{\perp,3}| \right) \\
 \text{subject to} \quad & R_{\text{eq},i}/\text{mm} = \arg \min_{R_{\text{eq},i}} f(R_{\text{eq},i}) - f_{\text{FM}}, \\
 & A_i, B_i/\text{mm} \in [20, 80], \\
 & a_i, b_i/\text{mm} \in [10, 60], \\
 & R_{i,i}/\text{mm} \in [60, 85], \\
 & L_i/\text{mm} = 93.5, \\
 & \alpha_i \geq 90^\circ, \\
 & \frac{E_{\text{pk}}}{E_{\text{acc}}} \leq 3, \\
 & \frac{B_{\text{pk}}}{E_{\text{acc}}} / \frac{\text{mT}}{\text{MV/m}} \leq 5,
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

where $f_{\text{FM}} = 801.58$ MHz.

A Pareto-based genetic algorithm is used to obtain a family of optimal solutions in a Pareto sense. The geometric properties of the selected cavity from this family of cavities are given in Table 5. The optimised cavity geometry is hereafter referred to as the C3795.

Table 5: Optimised mid-cell geometric parameters for the C3795 cavity geometry.

C3795 (Mid-cell) - Geometric Properties							
A_i [mm]	B_i [mm]	a_i [mm]	b_i [mm]	$R_{i,i}$ [mm]	L_i [mm]	$R_{\text{eq},i}$ [mm]	α_i [°]
62.22	66.13	30.22	23.11	72.00	93.50	171.20	94.50

The optimisation problem for the end-cell is stated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \min_{A_e, B_e, a_e, b_e, R_{i,e}} \left(\frac{E_{\text{pk}}}{E_{\text{acc}}}, \frac{B_{\text{pk}}}{E_{\text{acc}}}, -R/Q, |Z_{\parallel,1}|, |Z_{\parallel,2}|, |Z_{\perp,1}|, |Z_{\perp,2}|, |Z_{\perp,3}| \right) \\
 \text{subject to} \quad & L_e/\text{mm} = \arg \min_{L_e} f(L_e) - f_{\text{FM}}, \\
 & A_e, B_e/\text{mm} \in [20, 80], \\
 & a_e, b_e/\text{mm} \in [10, 60], \\
 & R_{i,e}/\text{mm} \in [72, 85], \\
 & \alpha_e \geq 90^\circ, \\
 & \frac{E_{\text{pk}}}{E_{\text{acc}}} \leq 3, \\
 & \frac{B_{\text{pk}}}{E_{\text{acc}}} / \frac{\text{mT}}{\text{MV/m}} \leq 5.
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

The selected cavity's end-cell geometric dimensions are given in Table 6. The FM and HOM QoIs of the whole cavity (mid-cell and end-cell) are presented in Table 7 and 8, respectively. The loss k_{\parallel} and kick k_{\perp} factors are given in Table 8 instead of the impedances because they quantify the average effect of the HOMs impedance.

Table 6: Optimised end-cell geometric parameters.

C3795 (End-cell) - Geometric Properties							
A_e [mm]	B_e [mm]	a_e [mm]	b_e [mm]	$R_{i,e}$ [mm]	L_e [mm]	$R_{eq,e}$ [mm]	α_e [°]
62.58	57.54	17.21	12.00	80.00	93.795	171.20	112.40

Table 7: FM QoIs of C3795 (mid- and end-cell).

C3795 - FM QoIs					
No. of cells	R/Q [Ω]	G [Ω]	$G.R/Q$ [$10^4\Omega^2$]	E_{pk}/E_{acc} [-]	B_{pk}/E_{acc} [$\frac{mT}{MV/m}$]
5	448.46	263.61	11.74	2.43	4.88

Table 8: HOMs QoIs of C3795 (mid- and end-cell).

C3795 - HOM QoIs			
No. of cells	$ k_{\parallel} $ [SR/BS]* [V/pC]	k_{\perp} [SR/BS]* [V/pC/m]	P_{HOM}/cav [SR/BS] [W]
5	2.639/2.083	2.014/2.396	748.64/549.72

* k_{\parallel} and k_{\perp} are the calculated loss and kick factors for the bare cavity using the synchrotron radiation (SR) and bremsstrahlung (BS) bunch lengths in Table 1.

3.2 Wakefield Impedance

The longitudinal and transverse wakefield impedance plots for the bare cavity are shown in Figures 5 and 6, respectively. Figure 5 shows that the frequency of the first longitudinal HOM is greater than the TM_{01} mode cutoff frequency ($f_{c, TM_{01}} = 1428$ MHz) of the beam pipe to which it couples.

Lossy eigenmode analysis is carried out on the cavity with the beam pipes terminated with waveguide ports. The longitudinal HOM impedances from this analysis are given in Table 9. The first longitudinal HOM passband spans frequencies between 1463.91 to 1700.98 MHz. Modes with $Q_{ext} > 1e5$, $R/Q >$

Figure 5: Longitudinal wakefield impedance plot for the C3795 cavity geometry (bare cavity) for a 100 m simulated wake length. The red circles mark some HOM peaks in the first longitudinal HOM passband.

10Ω and $Z_{||} > 0.5 \text{ k}\Omega$ are highlighted. The TM_{020} mode's impedance ($4.88 \text{ k}\Omega$) is the highest impedance in this passband.

Figure 6 shows the transverse wakefield impedance plot for the bare cavity. The high-impedance frequency modes are marked in this figure. The maximum frequency of the transverse HOMs in the first dipole passband is below the TE_{11} cutoff frequency ($f_{c,\text{TE}_{11}} = 1098.00 \text{ MHz}$) of the beampipe to which they couple. These modes, therefore, do not propagate out of the cavity and have, in theory, an infinite Q_{ext} if attached to an infinitely long beampipe. The beampipe attached to the cavity for the simulation has a finite length; therefore, we obtain a finite Q_{ext} given in Table 10. Table 10 also shows the transverse impedance values of the modes in this passband. The first transverse HOM passband spans frequencies between 930.62 to 1136.77 MHz. Modes with $R/Q > 10 \Omega$ are highlighted. The TM_{110} mode has the highest R/Q ($66.48 \text{ k}\Omega$) in this passband.

Later in this section, two couplers are optimised to dampen the impedance of these modes. Some damping schemes are also explored in this section.

Table 9: First HOM monopole passband modes properties for the bare cavity with waveguide ports beampipe termination. The electric field in all figures is scaled to a maximum value of 5000 MV/m.

C3975 - Impedance Properties (First longitudinal HOM passband)					
Mode	f [MHz]	Q_{ext} [·]	R/Q_{\parallel} [Ω]	Z_{\parallel} [k Ω]	E Field
TM011	1463.91	15.24	25.14	0.38	
TM011	1463.94	15.24	37.11	0.57	
TM011	1527.28	404.72	2.15	0.87	
TE011	1531.25	7.34e5	4.3e-7	3.16e-4	
TE011	1531.25	1.23e7	1.02e-6	1.26e-2	
TM011	1546.55	135.80	5.05	0.69	
TM011	1571.00	86.12	34.15	2.94	
TE011	1572.37	3.39e6	4.41e-7	1.49e-3	
TE011	1576.00	3.33e7	1.62e-6	5.37e-2	
TE011	1579.56	2.49e6	8.83e-7	2.2e-3	
TM020	1590.94	111.83	3.13	0.35	
TM020	1637.34	169.43	28.78	4.88	
TM020	1662.09	150.70	0.52	7.81e-2	
TM020	1684.41	230.05	0.19	4.31e-2	
TM020	1700.98	725.80	0.38	0.27	

3.3 Multipacting Analysis

The designed cavity geometry was analysed for multipacting using the 2D Multipac [12] code. Figure 7 shows the secondary emission yield (SEY) curve for niobium used for the analysis. Figures 8, 9, and 10 show the counter function c_{20}/c_0 , final impact energy Ef_{20} and enhanced counter function c_{20}/c_0 , respectively, for the C3975 cavity geometry. The counter functions are normalised with the total number of initial electrons released c_0 . The values on the y -axis of the counter and enhanced counter function plots could be interpreted as percentages of the initial number of electrons that survive after $N = 20$ impacts.

Figure 8 shows that about 21% of the initial number of electrons survive after

Figure 6: Transverse wakefield impedance plot for the C3795 cavity geometry (bare cavity) for a 100 m simulated wake length. The red circles mark some transverse HOM peaks.

Figure 7: SEY curve for niobium.

Figure 8: Counter function c_{20}/c_0 plotted against the peak electric field E_{pk} for the C3795 cavity geometry.

20 impacts for a peak electric field value of about 21 MV/m. At the operating surface peak field value of 60.05 MV/m, none of the electrons survives after 20 impacts. The figures indicate that soft multipacting could occur for accelerating field values between 8 MV/m to 16.5 MV/m. However, for the operating field value, no multipacting is expected because the secondary yield of electrons is

Table 10: First HOM dipole passband modes properties for the bare cavity with waveguide ports beampipe termination. The electric field in all figures is scaled to a maximum value of 5000 MV/m.

C3795 - Impedance Properties (First longitudinal HOM passband)					
Mode	f [MHz]	Q_{ext} [-]	R/Q_{\perp} [Ω]	Z_{\perp} [k Ω /m]	E Field
TE111	930.62	1.01e9	0.15	1.46e6	
TE111	930.62	1.38e8	0.15	2.00e5	
TM110	939.00	1.75e8	5.57	9.60e6	
TM110	939.01	1.00e8	5.60	5.53e6	
TE111	965.44	1.49e8	2.09	3.15e6	
TE111	965.44	1.89e8	2.09	3.99e6	
TE111	1002.44	1.62e9	44.30	7.56e8	
TE111	1002.45	5.63e8	44.17	2.61e8	
TM110	1038.22	1.24e8	66.26	8.90e7	
TM110	1038.22	5.51e7	66.48	3.99e7	
TM110	1050.56	1.36e9	9.14	1.37e8	
TM110	1050.57	4.92e8	9.22	5.00e7	
Modes with $f > f_{c,TE111}$					
TM110	1131.75	1.77e4	0.16	34.44	
TM110	1131.76	1.77e4	0.17	36.73	
TE111	1133.14	4.49e3	8.24	438.64	
TE111	1133.15	4.46e3	8.19	434.24	
TM110	1135.01	2.56e4	20.27	617.53	
TM110	1135.02	2.55e4	20.32	617.54	
TE111	1136.76	4.36e3	3.23	167.66	
TE111	1136.77	4.35e3	3.28	170.29	

less than one for field values that would sustain multipacting.

Figure 9: Final impact energy of particles $E f_{20}$ plotted against the peak electric field E_{pk} for the C3795 cavity geometry. The solid horizontal lines, from bottom to top, represent the first and second crossover energies, respectively. The dashed horizontal line represents the energy at the peak SEY.

Figure 10: Enhanced counter function e_{20}/c_0 plotted against the peak electric field E_{pk} for the C3795 cavity geometry. The solid horizontal line corresponds to $e_{20}/c_0 = 1$.

3.4 HOM Coupler Design (Outlook)

Tables 9 and 10 show the potentially parasitic HOMs properties for the bare cavity. In a preliminary study, the cavity is equipped with either four hook couplers (HCs) or four DQW couplers and analysed. Figure 11 shows a CST [15] model of the HC and the DQW HOM coupler.

Figure 11: Schematic of HC (left) and DQW (right) HOM coupler.

These couplers were tuned to maximise the scattering parameter S at the identified parasitic HOMs frequencies and minimise the S parameter at the FM frequency. For the HOM coupler tuning simulation setup, a waveguide port terminated beampipe is connected to the end of the coupler as shown in Figure 12. It was demonstrated in [3] that improved damping can be achieved by optimisation of the coupler using the cavity-coupler setup instead. Figure 13 shows the transmission properties of the tuned HOM couplers.

Figure 12: Simulation setup of HC (left) and DQW HOM coupler (right).

Figure 13: Transmission properties of the optimised HC and DQW HOM coupler.

3.5 HOM Coupler Systems

Lossy eigenmode analysis is performed with the tuned HOM couplers attached to the cavity. For each of the HOM coupler types, four of the couplers are

attached to the C3795 cavity and simulated. The following equations were used to calculate the longitudinal and transverse impedance from the lossy eigenmode analysis.

$$Z_{\parallel,n}(\omega) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{(R/Q)_{\parallel,n} \cdot Q_n}{1 + jQ_n \left(\frac{\omega_n}{\omega} - \frac{\omega}{\omega_n} \right)}, \quad (8)$$

$$Z_{\perp,n}(\omega) = \frac{c}{2\omega_n} \frac{(R/Q)_{\perp,n} \cdot Q_n}{1 + jQ_n \left(\frac{\omega_n}{\omega} - \frac{\omega}{\omega_n} \right)}, \quad (9)$$

where ω_n is the angular resonance frequency of mode n , $R/Q_{\parallel,n}$ and $R/Q_{\perp,n}$ are the longitudinal and transverse geometric shunt impedances of mode n , respectively, and Q_n is the external quality factor of mode n .

$$\frac{R}{Q_{\parallel,n}} = \frac{|V_{\parallel,n}(0,0)|^2}{\omega_n U_n}, \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{R}{Q_{\perp,n}} = \underbrace{\frac{|V_{\perp x,n}(0,0)|^2}{\omega_n U_n}}_{R/Q_{\perp x,n}} + \underbrace{\frac{|V_{\perp y,n}(0,0)|^2}{\omega_n U_n}}_{R/Q_{\perp y,n}}. \quad (11)$$

The impedance threshold is the impedance at which the beam instability's growth rate equals the instability's damping rate defined by the synchrotron radiation. The longitudinal and transverse impedance thresholds, $Z_{\parallel,\text{Th}}$, $Z_{\perp,\text{Th}}$, respectively, are calculated from [2] as follows:

$$Z_{\parallel,\text{Th}} = \frac{2(E/e)\nu_s}{N_c f I_0 \alpha_p \tau_z}, \quad (12)$$

$$Z_{\perp,\text{Th}} = \frac{2(E/e)}{N_c f_{\text{rev}} I_0 \beta_{xy} \tau_{xy}}. \quad (13)$$

The longitudinal impedance threshold is inversely proportional to the mode frequency, while the transverse impedance threshold is constant over the frequency range. The relevant machine parameters of the FCC-ee for calculating these thresholds are given in Table 11.

Four of the designed hook couplers, together with a fundamental power coupler (FPC) with an antenna of diameter 20.75 mm and housing diameter of 72.5 mm, are connected to the cavity system for all simulations. Wakefield and lossy eigenmode analyses are performed on the system. Two HOM couplers are placed on both sides of the cavity. This is to enable the extraction of HOM from both sides. A previous study [19] determined an optimal configuration for the cavity-HOM coupler system.

Figure 15 shows the longitudinal impedance plot from both the wakefield and lossy eigenmode simulations. The impedance plot of the bare cavity is also shown for reference. All the longitudinal HOM impedances are below the \bar{t} threshold.

Table 11: Some FCC-ee parameters [16][17][18] required to calculate beam stability threshold-impedance. The beta function in the cavity (β_{xy}) is assumed to be 50 m for all options.

	Description	Z	W	H*	tt*
f [MHz]	FM frequency	400	400	400	800
E [GeV]	Energy	45.6	80	120	182.5
I_0 [mA]	Beam current	1400	135	53.4	10
ν_s	Synchrotron oscillation tune	0.037	0.0801	0.0328	0.0826
α_p [10^{-6}]	Momentum compaction factor	28.5	28.5	7.33	7.33
τ_z [ms]	Longitudinal damping time	354.91	65.99	19.6	5.63
τ_{xy} [ms]	Transverse damping time	709.82	131.98	39.2	11.26
f_{rev} [kHz]	Revolution frequency	3.07	3.07	3.07	3.07
N_c	Number of cavities	56	112	236	380
$Z_{\parallel, \text{Th}}$ [k Ω]	Longitudinal impedance threshold	$\frac{4.26}{f[\text{GHz}]}$	$\frac{450.69}{f[\text{GHz}]}$	$\frac{4347.82}{f[\text{GHz}]}$	$\frac{192254.69}{f[\text{GHz}]}$
$Z_{\perp, \text{Th}}$ [k Ω /m]	Transverse impedance threshold	10.68	522.34	3164.93	55572.83

*For the H and tt operating points, the two beams are assumed to be accelerated by the same RF system.

Figure 14: (a) Front and (b) rear view of an optimal 4-hook coupler configuration.

Figure 16 shows the transverse impedance plot for the first HOM dipole modes passband. The figure also shows that the maximum transverse HOM impedance is lower than the tt transverse impedance threshold for both the HC and DQW systems. Due to the wide bandwidth of the first dipole passband, it might be profitable to optimise two separate couplers to have their peaks at different frequencies to obtain a sort of broadband damping in this bandwidth. This is yet to be studied.

Figure 15: Plot of the calculated longitudinal lossy eigenmode and wakefield impedances.

Figure 16: Plot of the calculated transverse lossy eigenmode and wakefield impedance.

4 5-cell Cavities Comparison

In this section, the properties of the designed cavity are compared with the properties of the FCCUROS5 for the $t\bar{t}$ operating point. In addition, they are both compared to a 5-cell TESLA cavity [9] scaled to operate at an FM frequency of 801.58 MHz.

4.1 Geometry

The geometric variables and values of the cavities are given in Table 12. Figure 17 shows the shape of the mid-cell and end-cell of the geometries.

Figure 17: Mid-cells (left) and end-cells (right) of compared cavities.

Table 12: Geometric parameters of C3795, FCCUROS5 and TESLA* cavities.

C3795, FCCUROS5, TESLA - Geometric Properties			
	C3795	FCCUROS5	TESLA
A [mm]	62.22/62.58	67.72/66.50	68.12/65.42/68.12
B [mm]	66.13/57.74	57.45/51.00	68.12/65.42/68.12
a [mm]	30.22/17.21	21.75/17.00	19.46/16.22/14.60
b [mm]	23.11/12.00	35.6/23.00	30.81/21.89/20.76
R_i [mm]	72.00/80.00	60.0/78.0	56.76/63.25/63.25
L [mm]	93.5/93.795	93.50/85.77	93.5/90.36/92.14
R_{eq} [mm]	171.20	166.591	167.61758
α [°]	94.50/112.40	100.00/96.87	103.17/106.03/107.31

*The dimensions of the TESLA cavity are scaled to operate at an FM frequency of 801.58 MHz.

The iris radius and wall angle are significant differences between the mid-cell geometry of the C3795 and the FCCUROS5 and TESLA geometries. The iris radius of the C3795 is about 16% and 21% greater than that for the FCCUROS5 and TESLA cavities, respectively. For the end-cell geometry, the C3795 and FCCUROS5 have similar iris radii with a 2.5% difference between them.

4.2 FM QoIs

Table 13 gives the FM QoIs and Figure 18 shows a bar plot of the relative difference between the FM QoIs for the compared cavities. The values are normalised with the maximum value of each QoI. The R/Q of C3795 is 16% less than that for the current baseline cavity and 24% less than that for the TESLA cavity. The geometric factor of C3795 is about 4% less than the value for both the FCCUROS5 and TESLA cavities. This implies a 4% reduction in Q_0 for the same material surface resistance R_s . For the peak field ratios, E_{pk}/E_{acc} is 16% greater and B_{pk}/E_{acc} is 11% greater when compared to the FCCUROS5. The percentage increase in peak electric and magnetic field ratios are 7% and 12%, respectively, when compared to the TESLA cavity.

Table 13: FM QoIs of the C3795, FCCUROS5 and TESLA cavity geometries.

C3795, FCCUROS5, TESLA - FM QoIs			
	C3795	FCCUROS5	TESLA
R/Q [Ω]	448.46	521.06	560.21
G [Ω]	263.61	272.93	271.65
$G \cdot R/Q$ [$10^4 \Omega^2$]	11.74	14.22	15.22
k_{cc} [%]	2.64	2.04	1.71
E_{pk}/E_{acc}	2.43	2.05	2.00
B_{pk}/E_{acc} [mT/MV/m]	4.88	4.33	4.20

The dispersion curve for the three cavities is shown in Figure 19. The C3795 cavity geometry has a greater coupling coefficient k_{cc} than the FCCUROS5 and TESLA cavities. The k_{cc} is calculated using

$$k_{cc} = 2 \times \frac{f_{\pi} - f_0}{f_{\pi} + f_0} \%, \quad (14)$$

where f_0 and f_{π} are the frequencies of the 0 and π phase advances of the TM_{010} mode.

Figure 18: Normalised bar plot of FM QoIs for the C3795, FCCUROS5 and TESLA cavity geometries.

The designed cavity performs worse than the FCCUROS5 and TESLA cav-

ities considering the FM QoIs except in k_{cc} . This is expected since the C3795 has a larger mid-cell iris radius which is strongly negatively correlated to the FM QoIs except in k_{cc} , which is positively correlated.

Figure 19: FM dispersion curve for the C3795, FCCUROS5 and TESLA cavity geometries.

4.3 HOM QoIs

The HOM QoIs for the compared cavities are given in Table 13. The loss factor of the FCCUROS5 cavity geometry is about 40% more than that of C3795, and its HOM power is 50% more than the HOM power of the designed cavity. The kick factor for the FCCUROS5 is an average of 73% greater than that for the designed cavity for the SR and BS bunch lengths. Overall, there is a significant improvement in the HOM performance of the C3795 compared to the FCCUROS5 cavity geometry. Figure 20 shows a bar plot of the normalised HOM QoIs of the compared cavities.

Table 14: HOM QoIs of the C3795, FCCUROS5 and TESLA cavity geometries.

C3795, FCCUROS5, TESLA - HOM QoIs			
	C3795	FCCUROS5	TESLA
$ k_{FM} [SR/BS]$ [V/pC]	0.564/0.563	0.656/0.655	0.703/0.702
$ k_{ } [SR/BS]$ [V/pC]	2.639/2.083	3.784/2.908	3.641/2.946
$k_{\perp}[SR/BS]$ [V/pC/m]	2.014/2.396	3.539/4.102	4.323/5.197
$P_{HOM}/cav[SR/BS]$ [W]	748.64/549.72	1132.66/815.75	1063.05/811.69

Figure 20: Normalised bar plot of HOM QoIs for the C3795, FCCUROS5 and TESLA cavity geometries.

4.4 Multipacting Analysis

The compared cavity geometries are analysed for multipacting. Figures 21, 22 and 23 show the counter, final impact energy and enhanced counter functions, respectively, for the three analysed cavity geometries. The operating fields of the three cavities are represented as dashed vertical lines on the plots. The letters F, T and C on the figures represent the FCCUROS5, TESLA and C3795 cavity operating peak field values, respectively. From the figures, it is concluded that multipacting does not occur for the three analysed cavities at the operating fields because the enhanced counter function value is less than one at these field values.

Figure 21: Counter function c_{20}/c_0 plotted against the peak electric field E_{pk} for the compared cavity geometries. F, T and C on the figures represent the FCCUROS5, TESLA and C3795 cavity operating peak field values, respectively.

Figure 22: Final impact energy of particles Ef_{20} plotted against the peak electric field E_{pk} for the compared cavities. The solid red horizontal lines, from bottom to top, represent the first and second crossover energies, respectively. The dashed red horizontal line represents the energy at the peak SEY.

Figure 23: Enhanced counter function e_{20}/c_0 plotted against the peak electric field E_{pk} for the compared cavities. The solid red horizontal line corresponds to $e_{20}/c_0 = 1$.

A strong multipacting barrier was observed in the JLab [10] cavity geometry at an accelerating field value of 11 MV/m ($E_{pk} = 24.86$ MV/m). With some high-power processing, it reached 31 MV/m during the first RF tests. However, in subsequent tests, strong multipacting was observed at $E_{acc} = 17$ MV/m ($E_{pk} = 38.42$ MV/m), which could not be processed away (Calaga, R., Dhakal, P., Rimmer, R., personal communication, February 06, 2023). Even after medium temperature (mid-T) baking, there was no significant improvement in the quality factor and multipacting. To make some inferences from the results from the JLab cavity geometry, the JLab cavity is analysed for multipacting using the Multipac code. The results from the analysis are compared with the results for the C3795 geometry.

Figures 24, 25 and 26 show the counter, final impact energy and enhanced counter functions, respectively, for the C3795 and JLab cavity geometries. Figure 24 shows that the peak field values that support multipacting for both cavities range from 18 MV/m to 40 MV/m. The final impact energy of the particles in this field range for the JLab cavity geometry is lower than the first cross-over energy for bulk Nb, which indicates that the SEY is less than one. Multipacting was, however, observed. Comparing the impact energy function

profile for the C3795 to the JLab cavity geometry, it can be concluded that the C3795 cavity geometry is more prone to multipacting than the JLab cavity geometry.

Figure 24: Counter function c_{20}/c_0 plotted against the peak electric field E_{pk} for the C3795 and JLab cavity geometries. J and C on the figures represent the JLab and C3795 cavity operating peak field values, respectively.

Figure 25: Final impact energy of particles Ef_{20} plotted against the peak electric field E_{pk} for the C3795 and JLab cavity geometries. The solid red horizontal lines, from bottom to top, represent the first and second crossover energies, respectively. The dashed red horizontal line represents the energy at the peak SEY.

Figure 26: Enhanced counter function e_{20}/c_0 plotted against the peak electric field E_{pk} for the C3795 and JLab cavity geometries. The solid red horizontal line corresponds to $e_{20}/c_0 = 1$.

4.5 Input Power and Cryogenic Heat Load

Information about the cavity wall material is required to calculate the cryogenic heat load. The following empirical formulas [11] are used to calculate the surface resistance of Nb/Cu at 4.5 K and bulkNb at 2 K, respectively.

$$R_s|_{\text{Nb/Cu@4.5K}} [\text{n}\Omega] \approx 39.5 \times E_{\text{acc}} \left(\frac{B_{\text{pk}}}{E_{\text{acc}}} \right) e^{0.014} + 27, \quad (15)$$

$$R_s|_{\text{bulkNb@2K}} [\text{n}\Omega] \approx 16.4 \times E_{\text{acc}} \left(\frac{B_{\text{pk}}}{E_{\text{acc}}} \right) \times 0.092 \left(\frac{800}{704} \right)^2. \quad (16)$$

The static and dynamic power losses and input power are calculated using equations 17, 18 and 19, respectively.

$$P_{\text{stat}} = \frac{V_{\text{RF}} \cdot L_{\text{cavity}}}{L_{\text{active}} \cdot E_{\text{acc}}} P_{\text{cryo}}, \quad (17)$$

$$P_{\text{dyn}} = V_{\text{RF}} \frac{E_{\text{acc}} \cdot L_{\text{active}}}{R/Q_{\parallel, \text{FM}} \cdot Q_0}, \quad (18)$$

$$P_{\text{in}} \approx \frac{P_{\text{SR}}}{N_{\text{cav}}}, \quad (19)$$

where P_{cryo} is the cryogenic power loss calculated as

$$P_{\text{cryo}} \approx \frac{8 \text{ W/m}}{\sqrt{f_{\text{FM}}/500 \text{ MHz}}}. \quad (20)$$

The total number of cavities required and the active length of one cavity are calculated as

$$N_{\text{cav}} = \frac{V_{\text{RF}}}{E_{\text{acc}} \cdot L_{\text{active}}}, \quad (21)$$

$$L_{\text{cavity}} = L_{\text{active}} + 2\lambda_0, \quad (22)$$

where λ_0 is the wavelength of the accelerating mode.

Figure 27 shows the plot of the static and dynamic power loss, input power per cavity and the number of cavities versus the accelerating field. The dotted vertical lines represent the considered operating accelerating electric field $E_{\text{acc}} = 24.72 \text{ MV/m}$. Figure 28 shows the input power plotted against the loaded quality factor Q_L assuming optimal detuning.

Table 15 gives the calculated static and dynamic power loss values and input power per cavity at the considered accelerating electric field. The C3795 cavity geometry has the highest dynamic power loss of approximately 62 kW, which is 27% and 33% greater than the dynamic power loss for the FCCUROS5 and TESLA cavity geometries, respectively. Figure 29 shows the bar plot of the normalised quantities for the compared cavity geometries.

Figure 27: Plot of static power loss P_{stat} , dynamic power loss P_{dyn} , number of cavities N_{cav} and input power per cavity P_{in}/cav versus accelerating field E_{acc} .

Figure 28: Input power P_{in} as a function of loaded quality factor $Q_{L,0}$ assuming optimal detuning. Q_L^* represents the optimum loaded quality factor.

Figure 29: Normalised bar plot of the number of cavities, dynamic power losses, HOM power loss and total power loss for C3795, FCCUROS5 and TESLA cavity geometries.

Table 15: Static and dynamic power loss and input power per cavity for C3795, FCCUROS5, and TESLA cavity geometries.

C3795, FCCUROS5, TESLA - Power Analysis			
	C3795	FCCUROS5	TESLA
N_{cav}		380	
Q_0 [10^9]	7.36	8.05	7.87
R_s [$\text{n}\Omega$]	35.54	33.92	34.55
P_{stat} [W]		4038.10	
P_{dyn} [W]	61759.10	48640.91	46415.73
$P_{\text{HOM,tot}}$ [SR][W]	284240	430160	403940
$P_{\text{loss,tot}}$ [kW]	350.04	482.84	454.39
$P_{\text{in/cav}}$ [kW]		131.67	

5 H Operating Point Options Comparison

This section compares the 2-cell cavity (C3794) designed for the W operating point operating at 400.79 MHz FM frequency [3], the same 2-cell cavity scaled to operate at 801.58 MHz FM frequency, and a 5-cell cavity operating at 801.58 MHz FM frequency for the H working point. For brevity, the 2-cell cavity operating at 400.79 MHz is called C3794@400MHz, and the 2-cell cavity operating at 801.58 MHz is referred to as C3794@800MHz. In this comparison, it is crucial to keep in mind that the C3794 and C3795 cavity geometries are optimised with different constraints for different operating points. Therefore, the following comparisons only give an idea of obtainable QoIs values considering a parameter set over another.

The assumed operating field and cavity wall material for the considered options are listed in Table 16. Table 17 shows the geometric parameters of the compared cavities.

Table 16: Table showing the considered parameter sets for the H operating point.

C3794@400MHz, C3794@800MHz, C3795 - H operating point parameters			
	C3794@400MHz	C3794@800MHz	C3795
Cells/cav	2	2	5
f [MHz]	400.79	801.58	801.58
E_{acc} [MV/m]	11.87	11.87	24.72
Cavity wall material	Nb/Cu	bulk Nb	bulk Nb

Table 17: Geometric parameters of the C3794@400MHz, C3794@800MHz, and C3795 cavities.

Geometric Properties			
	C3794@400MHz	C3794@800MHz	C3795
No. of cells	2	2	5
f [MHz]	400.79	801.58	801.58
A/A_e [mm]	73.52	36.76	62.22/62.58
B/B_e [mm]	131.75	65.875	66.13/57.54
a/a_e [mm]	106.25	53.125	30.22/17.21
b/b_e [mm]	118.7	59.35	23.11/12.00
$R_i/R_{i,e}$ [mm]	150	75	72.00/80.00
L/L_e [mm]	187	93.5	93.5/93.795
R_{eq} [mm]	369.63	184.6653	171.20
α_i/α_e [°]	107.23	107.23	94.50/112.40

5.1 FM QoIs

Table 18 shows the FM QoIs of the cavities. The FM QoIs are invariant to frequency scaling; therefore, these values do not change for the C3794 cavity geometry when scaled to operate at 801.58 MHz. Figure 30 shows a normalised bar plot for the different cavity and frequency options. The parameters in Table 18 are independent of the number of cells except for the R/Q , which scales linearly with the number of cells.

Table 18: FM QoIs of the C3794 and C3795 cavity geometries.

C3794 (400 MHz/800 MHz), C3795 - FM QoIs		
	C3794	C3795
R/Q [Ω]	152.80	448.46
k_{cc} [%]	1.15	2.64
G [Ω]	198.42	261.63
$G.R/Q$ [$10^4\Omega^2$]	3.03	11.74
E_{pk}/E_{acc}	2.05	2.43
B_{pk}/E_{acc} [mT/MV/m]	6.39	4.88

*The C3794 and C3795 cavity geometries are optimised with different constraints for different operating points. Therefore, the values in this table only give an idea of obtainable QoIs values considering a parameter set over another.

Figure 30: Normalised bar plot of FM QoIs for C3794@400MHz, C3794@800MHz, and C3795 cavities.

5.2 HOM QoIs

Table 19 shows the HOM QoIs for the compared cavities. The C3795 option has the highest loss and kick factors and HOM power. This is expected as the loss and kick factors scale linearly with the number of cells per cavity and inversely with geometric dimensions. Opting for a higher frequency and a higher number of cells increases the HOM losses. All longitudinal HOM impedance values are less than the H longitudinal threshold value. Therefore, only the transverse HOMs impedances are discussed.

It was shown in [3] that the maximum transverse HOM impedance for the C3794@400MHz is below the W transverse impedance threshold and, consequently, below the H transverse impedance threshold value. The question to answer, therefore, is if the maximum transverse impedances for the C3794@800MHz and C3795 are below the H operating point threshold.

Table 19: HOM QoIs of C3794 and C3795.

C3794 (400 MHz/800 MHz), C3795 - HOM Properties			
	C3794@400MHz	C3794@800MHz	C3795
f [MHz]	400.79	801.58	801.58
σ [mm]		2.5	
I_0 [mA]		53.4	
$ k_{FM} $ [SR/BS][V/pC]	0.096/0.096	0.096/0.096	0.281/0.281
$ k_{ } $ [SR/BS][V/pC]	0.5908/0.4198	0.7831/0.5535	2.112/1.564
k_{\perp} [SR/BS][V/pC/m]	0.1828/0.231	0.9667/1.197	2.384/3.046
P_{HOM}/cav [SR/BS][W]	639.06/418.29	887.48/591.01	2365.10/1657.57

*The C3794 and C3795 cavity geometries are optimised with different constraints for different operating points. Therefore, the values in this table only give an idea of obtainable QoIs values considering a parameter set over another.

The maximum transverse HOM impedance is about 205 k Ω /m for a four 2-cell (C3794@800MHz) cavity module from Figure 31. The threshold transverse

impedance value of approximately $6288 \text{ k}\Omega/\text{m}$ is about 30 times the maximum HOM transverse impedance.

Figure 32 shows the first dipole passband modes impedance for a four 5-cell HOM damped cavity module. The figure shows that the maximum impedance for the module is below the transverse impedance threshold for the H operating point. The transverse impedance threshold is approximately $32828 \text{ k}\Omega/\text{m}$. It is 3.4 times greater than the module's maximum transverse impedance, approximately $9791 \text{ k}\Omega/\text{m}$.

Figure 31: Transverse impedance plot for a module consisting of four C3794 cavities @800 MHz, each damped with four HCs. The impedance threshold is normalised to the number of modules required for the H operating point.

Figure 33 shows a normalised bar plot for the HOM QoIs of the compared cavities. There is a 25% increase in loss factor and a 16% increase in HOM power scaling the C3794 cavity geometry from 400 MHz to 800 MHz. The kick factor increases by 81%.

Figure 32: Transverse impedance plot for a module consisting of four C3795 cavities, each damped with four hook couplers. The impedance threshold is normalised to the number of modules required for the H operating point.

Figure 33: Normalised bar plot of HOM QoIs for C3794@400MHz, C3794@800MHz, and C3795 cavities.

5.3 Input power and cryogenic heat load

Figure 34 shows the static and dynamic power losses, input power and the required number of cavities plotted against the accelerating field. The considered accelerating fields are represented with dotted vertical lines. Figure 35 shows the input power plotted against the loaded quality factor Q_L assuming optimal detuning.

The static and dynamic power losses, input power and required number of cavities are given in Table 20 for the assumed accelerating electric field values, i.e. 11.87 MV/m for C3794 and 24.72 MV/m for C3795. The input power required for 5-cell cavities operating at 800 MHz is about 552 kW. For C3794@400MHz, the input power is 210 kW, and for C3794@800MHz, the input

Figure 34: Plot of static power loss per cavity P_{stat} , dynamic power loss per cavity P_{dyn} , number of cavities per beam N_{cav} and input power per cavity $P_{\text{in}/\text{cav}}$ versus accelerating field E_{acc} .

Figure 35: Input power P_{in} as a function of loaded quality factor $Q_{L,0}$ assuming optimal detuning. Q_L^* represents the optimum loaded quality factor.

power is 105 kW. Figure 36 shows a bar plot of the normalised values.

The following conclusions can be made for the assumed accelerating fields E_{acc} . The 5-cell option operating at 800 MHz requires the least number of cavities. The C3794@400MHz option requires about 2.6 times more cavities. The C3794@800MHz option requires the most cavities, twice that of the C3794@400MHz option. The number of cavities required for the C3794@800MHz option can be reduced by operating the cavity at a higher accelerating electric field. The static power loss is also reduced for higher accelerating field values. However, this comes at the cost of increased dynamic losses.

Table 21 shows the total static and dynamic power losses, input and HOM power calculated for the different options. The total dynamic loss for the C3794@800MHz option is the lowest, with a value of 9.23 kW. The C3795 cavity geometry, however, can be optimised for comparable dynamic power loss to the

Table 20: Static, dynamic power loss and input power for C3794@400MHz, C3794@800MHz, and C3795 cavities.

C3795 - Power Analysis			
	C3794@400MHz	C3794@800MHz	C3795
N_{cav}	238	475	91
$N_{\text{cells,tot}}$	476	950	455
Q_0 [10^9]	1.41	6.59	7.36
R_s [n Ω]	140.85	30.16	35.54
P_{stat} [W]	4761.25	3366.71	963.64
P_{dyn} [W]	86232.80	9233.71	14750.74
$P_{\text{in/cav}}$ [kW]	210.57	105.28	551.77

*The C3794 and C3795 cavity geometries are optimised with different constraints for different operating points. Therefore, the values in this table only give an idea of obtainable QoIs values considering a parameter set over another.

Figure 36: Normalised bar plot of the number of cavities, static and dynamic power loss, input power, HOM power and total power loss for C3794@400MHz, C3794@800MHz, and C3795 cavities.

C3794@800MHz option. The dynamic loss for the C3794@400MHz option is about one order of magnitude greater than that for the C3794@800MHz option. Overall, the total power loss for the C3794@400MHz and C3795 options are comparable. The total power loss for the C3794@800MHz option is about two times the value for the C3794@400MHz.

Table 21: Summary of the total input power and power loss for the C3794@400MHz, C3794@800MHz and C3795 cavity options.

C3794@400MHz, C3794@800MHz, C3795 - Total Input Power and Power Loss			
	C3794@400MHz	C3794@800MHz	C3795
Cells/cav	2	2	5
f [MHz]	400.79	801.58	801.58
E_{acc} [MV/m]	11.87	11.87	24.72
N_{cav}	238	475	91
Total Power Input			
$P_{\text{in,tot}}$ [MW]	50.11	50.00	50.20
Total Power Loss			
P_{stat} [kW]	4.76	3.37	0.96
P_{dyn} [kW]	86.23	9.23	14.75
$P_{\text{HOM,tot}}$ [SR][kW]	152.10	421.55	215.22
$P_{\text{loss,tot}}$ [kW]	243.09	434.15	230.93

Again, this value could be reduced by operating the cavity at higher accelerating fields. Figure 37 shows a normalised bar plot for the number of cavities and the static and dynamic power losses for compared cavities, including the C3794@800MHz operating at an accelerating field of 23.74 MV/m. The bar plot shows a reduction in the number of cells required and the static losses by half and an increase in the dynamic power loss and input power.

Figure 37: Normalised bar plot of the number of cavities, static and dynamic power loss, input power, HOM power and total power loss for C3794@400MHz, C3794@800MHz@11.87MV/m, C3794@800MHz@23.74MV/m, and C3795 cavities.

6 Summary and Conclusion

A 5-cell elliptical cavity geometry (C3795) was optimised for operation at the $\bar{t}\bar{t}$ operating point. The designed cavity is compared with the present baseline cavity geometry (FCCURO5) and the TESLA cavity geometry. The analysis showed that the FCCURO5 cavity remains a good option for the $\bar{t}\bar{t}$ operating point. The designed cavity performed better only in terms of HOM power and kick factor. The HOM power is 50% more for the FCCURO5 than for the C3795 cavity geometry, while the peak electric and magnetic field ratios increased by 7% and 12%, respectively. Since the maximum longitudinal and transverse impedance of the FCCURO5 cavity is below the threshold value, there is not much incentive to go for the C3795 cavity geometry. However, the C3795 cavity geometry is better suited for the booster cavities of the Z-working point than the FCCURO5 cavity geometry.

Three cavity options operating at different field values and frequencies were considered for the H operating point. The first option is a 2-cell cavity operating at an FM frequency of 400.79 MHz (C3794@400MHz) and an accelerating field of 11.87 MV/m. The second option is a scaled version of the same 2-cell cavity operating at an FM frequency of 801.58 MHz (C3794@800MHz) and an accelerating field of 11.87 MV/m. The third option is a 5-cell cavity operating at an FM frequency of 801.58 MHz (C3795) and an accelerating field of 24.72 MV/m. The maximum HOM transverse impedance of the three options was below the transverse impedance threshold for a four-cavity module. The total power loss (total HOM power included) for the C3794@400MHz and C3795 options was 243.09 kW and 230.93 kW, respectively. The total power loss for the C3794@400MHz option was 434.15 kW, almost twice the value for the other options. This value, however, could be reduced by operating the cavity at higher operating fields. For example, operating the C3794@800MHz at twice the assumed accelerating field of 11.87 MV/m, i.e. at 23.74 MV/m, would reduce the HOM power by half and, consequently, the total power loss. The considered C3795 cavity geometry option for the H operating point does not allow for much beam current increment. Further investigation is needed to determine if the maximum impedance can be lowered further for this option. The conservative options would therefore be the C3794@400MHz and C3794@800MHz. It is, however, quite difficult to operate a 2-cell cavity at 800 MHz at accelerating field values over 10 MV/m. This leaves the C3794@400MHz as the preferred option.

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